

Colloid Chemical Analysis. Part II.

BY JNANENDRANATH MUKHERJEE, SATYAPRASAD ROYCHOUDHURY,
SAROJ KUMAR DAS-GUPTA, AMIYA KUMAR SEN, BIMALRANJAN
MAZUMDAR AND ASUTOSH CHATTERJEE.

In the introduction to the first paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 373) attention has been drawn to the uncertainties regarding the fundamental concepts concerning the electrical properties of colloids. The present paper deals with further experimental work. Theoretical considerations relevant to the subject matter of this paper are briefly referred to as they will be discussed in a series of papers to appear in the *Kolloid Zeitschrift* (*cf.* Mukherjee, *Kolloid Z.*, 1933, 62, 257; 1933, 63, 36).

A. Theoretical Considerations.

1. The Helmholtz-Smoluchowski theory of cataphoretic motion gives the specific conductivity, K_1 of a colloidal solution, free from intermicellary electrolytes and neglecting the conductivity of the ions of water, as follows:—

$$K_1 = C \cdot u \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

C is the number of electrochemical equivalents of free charge carried by the colloidal particles per c. c. which is equal to that carried by the mobile ions and u is the equivalent conductivity of the charged colloidal particle, *i.e.*, the cataphoretic speed multiplied by F , the Faraday quantity of electricity. According to this theory the mobile ions take no part in the transport of electricity and their transport number is zero while that of the charged colloidal particle is unity. On the other hand according to the chemical school, built up by Duclaux, MacBain and Pauli and coworkers, (*vide* Pauli and Valko, "Electrochemie der Kolloide," 1929, for a systematic exposition) the specific conductivity is given by the following equation

$$K_1 = C (u + v) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where K_1 , C and u have the same significance as in equation (1) and

v is the equivalent conductivity of the mobile ions which are assumed to be all of the same kind.

2. The difficulty of ascertaining which of these equations is confirmed by observations rests on the uncertainty of determining the value of C and to a less extent of v . In most colloidal solutions intermicellary electrolytes* are present and the ions associated with the colloid are often partly present as mobile ions in the intermicellary liquid. The specific conductivity K of such solutions is given by

$$K = K_1 + K_2 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

K_1 and K_2 are respectively the specific conductivities of (a) the charged colloidal particles and their mobile ions and (b) of the intermicellary electrolytes. In order to ascertain the conductivity and composition of the charged colloidal particles and their associated ions, Duclaux, Zsigmondy and MacBain and coworkers assumed that the ultrafiltrate has the same composition as that of the intermicellary liquid. From the differences in the conductivity and composition of the colloidal solution and of the ultrafiltrate, those of the colloid and associated ions are calculated. Pauli pointed out, that the ultrafiltrate should not, from the point of view of Donnan's theory of membrane potential, have the same composition as the intermicellary liquid. He made simultaneous measurements of the activities of ions in the solution. The experimental results which follow show how far-reaching changes can be produced by ultrafiltration (*cf.* Part I, *loc. cit.*). Unfortunately the activity coefficients of ions in these solutions are unknown. A further complication arises from the well known fact, established by the work of Duclaux and MacBain and his coworkers, that part of the ions carrying a charge of opposite sign to that of the colloidal particles moves with the latter in an electric field. The chemical school in analogy with the usual concepts of electrochemistry interprets this fact as indicating incomplete dissociation (classical theory), or, complete ionisation together with a limited association of

* Duclaux designated the charged colloidal particle together with the associated mobile ions (formed by dissociation in his opinion) as a micelle (*vide* Zsigmondy, *Kolloid chemie*, 3rd Edition, 1920. p. 126). The 'free' electrolytes present in the sol other than the charged colloidal particle and the associated mobile ions were also designated by him as intermicellary electrolytes.

ions (Pauli and Valko, *loc. cit.*). At any rate since the same ions are present in most cases as mobile ions and also as ions of the intermicellary electrolytes, the actual concentration of the mobile ions as such is less and different from their total concentration in the sol.

3. Whereas the chemical school deals with the activities, conductivities, molecular and ionic constitution and related properties, they are rather cursorily discussed in orthodox text books of colloids. The so-called physical school is concerned mostly with potentials of the double layer, its thickness, capacity and changes in interfacial tension. The distribution of the electric charges is considered as in metallic condensers and the actual distribution of the ions is overlooked. The properties of the primarily adsorbed ions including their valencies and the equilibrium distribution of ions between the surface, the mobile layer and the solution, appear to be the main factors whose detailed consideration is necessary for a proper understanding of the electrical properties of colloids. A rational picture of the double layer and the equilibrium distribution of ions on this basis was first discussed by one of us in 1921 (Mukherjee, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1921, 16. 103) and the general outline given there has been developed in subsequent papers. According to this point of view one would expect a characteristic behaviour of colloidal solutions. Briefly stated, the differences with usual simple electrolytes arise out of the distribution of the electrical charges, the adsorption (primary and electrical) of ions and the 'non-homogeneous' (in the sense of Gibbs' phase rule definitions) nature of the interface. For example, mobile ions are thickly distributed adjacent to the colloidal particles and in addition to interionic attraction, formulated by one of us as electrical adsorption (*loc. cit.*), also interionic repulsion has to be considered (*vide* Mukherjee, *Thesis, University of London*, 1921). The electrical potential of the region in which the ion finds itself is a factor determining the activity coefficient of an ion and the manner of distribution of the electrical charges determines this potential. Irreversible and reversible changes arising out of the agglomeration also take place. Besides, the activities of the primary and electrically adsorbed ions, which are either 'actual' or 'possible' components of the surface (in the sense in which these terms have been defined by Gibbs) cannot be interpreted without reference to the interaction with the surface (*Proc. Ind. Science Congress*, 1929, p. 96). This does not necessarily imply that the activity

coefficient is not, in suitable cases, determined by the electrical potential. Another point of difference may be mentioned. It arises out of what is meant by the valency of the charged colloidal particles, the "colloidal" ions of the chemical school (Pauli and Valko, *loc. cit.*, give values for the valency from 10 to 200,000). The total free charge of a colloidal particle is evidently the sum of the charges carried by the primarily adsorbed ions on its surface. Assuming the latter to consist only of ions of one kind, the total free charge would be given by the product of the valency of each ion with the number of such ions on the surface of the particle. According to the chemical school the total free charge denotes the valency of the 'colloidal' ion. It appears that the valency of the primarily adsorbed ions is the more important factor and the valency (*i.e.*, the total charge which from analogy with electrolytic ions gives the valency) of the 'colloidal ion' as a whole has a secondary significance.

B. *The Discrepancy between Activity and Conductivity Measurements in Colloidal Solutions.*

1. The measurements of activities and conductivities of ferric oxide sols given in Part I (*loc. cit.*) show that it is difficult to reconcile the observed activities with the conductivities; the latter are too high. The hydrogen ion activity in this sol cannot be directly measured and was determined after coagulation with solid potassium sulphate following Pauli who used potassium chloride. Pauli and Valko (*loc. cit.*, p. 309) also mention that the observed conductivity is high and in some cases requires the assumption of an equivalent conductivity of 118 at 25° for the positive carriers other than hydrogen ions. As no such cation has so far been discovered, this in itself is an observation of considerable interest.

2. The following table gives the conductivities calculated from the measurement at 20.5° given in Part I (*loc. cit.*). The specific conductivities in column 3 (Table I) have been calculated as follows: From the experimentally measured activities of the chlorine ions, their total concentration in the sol in the free state is calculated on the assumption that the activity coefficient is unity. The concentration calculated per c. c. multiplied by the equivalent conductivity of chlorine ions at infinite dilution at 20.5° gives the contribution of these ions to the specific conductivity. The activity of hydrogen ions measured after coagulation gives similarly their contri-

bution to the specific conductivity. Assuming the chlorine ions to be the only negatively charged carriers of electricity, the equivalent conductivity of all the positively charged carriers is given by the excess of the concentration of chlorine ions over that of the hydrogen ions. The positively charged carriers are the charged colloidal particles and possibly usual electrolytic ions containing iron, *e.g.*, ferric ions. As the relative concentrations of these ions are unknown, the contribution of the positively charged carriers has been calculated assuming either that there are no electrolytic ions containing iron or that there are only ferric ions and no other positively charged carriers.

The following equivalent conductivities at infinite dilution at 20.5° have been used: $H^{\circ} = 327$; $Cl^{\circ} = 70.3$; $\frac{1}{3} Fe^{\circ\circ\circ} = 64$. The cathoretic speed was directly measured by the boundary methods. The large values of the equivalent conductivity cannot be reconciled with the activity measurement.

TABLE I.

Dilution X.	$K_{obs.} \times 10^4$.	$K_{calc.} \times 10^4$.		$K_{obs.} / K_{calc.}$		$[\Delta_v]_{Cl}$			
		Colloid ions (1)	Ferric ions (2)	(1)	(2)	(1)		(2)	
						γ	δ	γ	δ
1	10.39	4.41	4.60	2.36	2.26	30.5	270.7	21.5	235.7
2	5.60	2.97	3.59	1.88	1.56	54.17	203.4	18.2	166.4
4	3.08	1.37	1.66	2.25	1.86	70.3	243	40.3	213
6	2.17	0.93	1.10	2.33	1.96	76.3	259.3	49.3	232.3
11	1.18	0.59	0.70	2.00	1.7	76.1	206.1	52.1	182.1

The equivalent conductivities γ and δ of the chlorine ions have been calculated in two ways: assuming that besides hydrogen ions there are (i) only charged colloidal particles which carry positive electricity and (ii) that alternatively only ferric ions are present. The equivalent conductivity $[\Delta_v]_{Cl}$ is given as follows:

$$[\Delta_v]_{Cl} = \Delta_v - [\Delta_u]_{coll \text{ or } \frac{1}{3} Fe^{\circ\circ\circ}} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

where Δ_v is the equivalent conductivity of the "colloid" chloride and $[\Delta_u]$ for 'coll,' or, $\frac{1}{3} Fe^{\circ\circ\circ}$, is that of the "colloidal" ions or of the ferric ions. Δ_v has been calculated in two ways:

namely, (a) by subtracting the concentration of the hydrogen ions, $C_{H^{\circ}}$ from $N_{Cl'}$, the total chlorine concentration; this gives the total chlorine associated with the colloid (γ value); and (b) by subtracting $C_{H^{\circ}}$ from $C_{Cl'}$ the concentration of the free chlorine ions (calculated from the activity as stated above).

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \Delta_v &= \frac{1000. (K - K_{HCl})}{N_{Cl'} - C_{H^{\circ}}} & \dots & \gamma \\ \Delta_v &= \frac{1000. (K - K_{HCl})}{C_{Cl'} - C_{H^{\circ}}} & \dots & \delta \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

The equivalent concentration of 'colloid' ions or of ferric ions is given by $C_{Cl'} - C_{H^{\circ}}$.

3. In Part I (*loc. cit.*) a method has been indicated for testing experimentally the hypothesis that the surface density of charge runs parallel, within certain limits, to the cataphoretic speed. This proposition can be reconciled with the Helmholtz-Smoluchowski and the Debye-Hückel theories of cataphoresis (Mukherjee, *Kolloid Z.*, 1933, 62, 263). In view of the uncertainties in determining C and the activity and conductivity coefficients it is not possible to apply this method till these quantities can be unequivocally ascertained. Other sources of evidence in support of this hypothesis will be discussed elsewhere (*Kolloid Z.*). In order to reconcile the variations of the cataphoretic speed with this hypothesis, the following assumptions were made (the concentration of the colloidal particles is taken to be proportional to the dilution):

(a) The positively charged carriers in the sol consist of hydrogen, ferric (and perhaps other electrolytic ions containing iron) ions and charged colloidal particles. The equivalent concentration of the latter is comparatively small and the observed chlorine ion activity may be attributed to the free chlorine ions, associated with the ferric ions and with the hydrogen ions.

(b) The activity and conductivity coefficients are unity.

(c) The mobility of the charged colloidal particles is to be increased by a constant factor assumed in the calculation to be equal to that of the chlorine ions. The last assumption is quite arbitrary. The above illustrates that the interpretation of the activity and conductivity measurements constitutes the first step towards the theoretical elucidation of the subject.

4. Pauli and Valko (*loc. cit.*, p. 311) refer to the advantage which aluminium oxide sols possess in that the activities of both hydrogen and chlorine ions can be measured. They show (Pauli and Valko, *loc. cit.*, pp. 311-314) that the equivalent conductivity increases regularly with the dilution and that the ratio of the equivalent conductivity to the equivalent activity is constant (*vide* column 4 of Table II which reproduces their data). The constancy of this ratio signifies that throughout the range of dilutions the conductivity coefficient also varies proportionally. Such a coincidence will be remarkable even for a true electrolyte and a difference and not a strict proportionality is expected on theoretical grounds. Besides, the assumption that all the chlorine atoms exist as free ions requires independent experimental proof.

TABLE II.

Aluminium oxide sol (Pauli and Valko).

Dilution X.	Equivalent conductivity of 'colloid' chloride.	Equivalent chloridion activity $\times 10^4$.	Ratio of equivalent conductivity to activity.	Activity coefficient.
1	54.82	281	19.5	0.387
2	59.74	301	19.8	0.392
4	64.75	318.2	20.5	0.440
8	71.13	348.0	20.4	0.492
16	79.11	370.6	20.3	0.516
32	84.85	394.5	21.5	0.547
64	91.0	421.5	21.6	0.598
128	97.17	469.9	20.6	0.619
256	105.4	483.8	21.8	0.761

5. On calculating their results differences are observed between the measured and calculated conductivities (Table III). It will also be seen that the equivalent conductivity at infinite dilution, calculated on the assumption that the activity coefficient is equal to the conductivity coefficient, regularly *decreases* at the higher dilutions.

TABLE III.

Dilution. X	Sp. conductivity $\times 10^5$		Equiv. conducti- vity at infinite dilu- tion at 25°.
	Obs.	Calc.	
1	400.2	345	141.7
2	218.9	176.1	152.4
4	119	99.4	147.1
8	66.3	56.3	144.5
16	37.4	30.2	153.3
32	20.13	16.6	155.2
64	11.36	9.47	152.2
128	6.4	5.6	143.1
256	3.6	3.26	137.4

The following equivalent conductivities at 25° have been used in the above calculations: $H^+ = 350$, $Cl^- = 75$, $1/3Al^{+++} = 47$. The equivalent concentration $C_{1/3Al^{+++}}$ of aluminium ions has been taken to be equal to $C_{Cl^-} - C_{H^+}$.

6. The hydrogen ion concentrations of these aluminium oxide sols are relatively large. Free aluminium ions in solution are probably stable below a p_H equal to 4 (Britton, "Hydrogen Ion Concentration", 1929) and it is difficult to ascertain the relative proportion of the positive charges carried by aluminium ions and colloidal aluminium oxide.

C. The Characteristic Behaviour of Colloids.

Pauli and Valko (*loc. cit.*) have discussed other observations which show that the conductivities and activities of ions of these colloidal solutions are often difficult to reconcile with each other as also with their osmotic pressures. They, however, conclude (*loc. cit.* p. 317) that the modern theory of interionic attraction together with the assumption of a suitable association factor can explain these differences. The data given in the following pages show that the activities of the ions of these solutions cannot be reconciled with the conductivity. Indeed both the chemical and physical theories fail to account for the observations. These colloidal solutions in fact behave in a manner which characterises them.

The experimental work recorded in this paper deals with the following subjects :

EXPERIMENTAL.

(a) The ultrafiltrate of aluminium oxide sols having a relatively high hydrogen ion concentration has been analytically examined. Free aluminium ions are possibly present. The conductivities and the activities of the ions of a number of aluminium oxide sols having increasing p_H values have been measured and the cataphoretic velocity of the colloid has been also measured by the boundary method. One sol has been titrated with baryta and the change in conductivity, p_H and chlorine ion activity has been measured simultaneously.

(b) Similar measurements have been made with silicic acid sols.

I. *Experiments with Sol A. Aluminium Oxide Sols.*

Preparation of the sol.—The sol was prepared by adding to a litre of normal aluminium chloride solution slightly less than the equivalent amount of normal ammonia solution. A precipitate was formed which on vigorous stirring was stopped and on keeping overnight a perfectly clear sol was formed. The sol was dialysed in a parchment paper against repeated changes of hot distilled water. After dialysis had been continued for about a month and a half the sol was found to be turbid and more suitable for measurements of charge by the boundary method. The dialysis was then stopped.

Measurements of cataphoretic speed.—The cataphoretic speed of the colloidal particles was measured by the method of moving boundaries as modified by Mukherjee (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923, **103A**, 102). Aluminium hydroxide sol, however, being colourless, a dark background illumination was devised which enabled the boundary to be distinctly visible. For upper liquid a hydrochloric acid solution was prepared having the same p_H as the sol. To this acid solution a concentrated solution of aluminium chloride was added drop by drop until the resulting mixture was of slightly greater conductivity than that of the sol. By this procedure the potential gradient and also the upward and downward movements of the boundary was found to remain constant. For the sake of comparison the ultrafiltrate was also employed as the upper

liquid. In this case also the potential gradient remained remarkably constant and the upward and downward movements of the cataphoretic speeds agreed with the results obtained when the other procedure was employed.

Measurements of chlorine ion concentration.—The concentration of chlorine ions was determined by means of silver—silver chloride electrodes. The electrodes were prepared according to the method of Noyes and Ellis (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **39**, 2532).

Determination of total chloride.—The total chloride of aluminium hydroxide sol was determined by potentiometric titration with a standard solution of silver nitrate. A concentration cell was set up with the solution whose total chloride was to be determined and a saturated AgCl solution as the other electrode. Both the solutions contained 5% KNO₃. The connecting salt bridge was a saturated solution of KNO₃. The *E.M.F.* gradually decreased and when all the chloride was precipitated by AgNO₃, the sign of the *E.M.F.* was reversed. The end points were read off from the graphs as usual.

Hydrogen ion concentration.—The hydrogen ion concentration of the sol was determined by means of a hydrogen (quinhydrone was also used) electrode. A normal calomel electrode and a K-type Leeds Northrup potentiometer were employed.

The ultrafiltrates.—35 C.c. of the aluminium hydroxide sol was filtered through ultrafilters prepared from a high concentration of collodion in an open pattern nickel plated apparatus and 25 c.c. filtrate collected. This is the first portion of the filtrate. The sol left on the ultrafilter was collected separately. Again 35 c.c. sol were placed on the filter and filtered till 25 c. c. of the fresh filtrate were collected. This is the second portion of the filtrate. The sol left on the filter this time was mixed with that of the previous operation and the mixture constitutes the 'residual' sol.

TABLE IV.

Composition of the sol.

	Sp. conductivity × 10 ³ .	Activity of Cl ion × 10 ² .	Total chlorine × 10 ² .	Hydrogen ion conc. × 10 ³ .
A	1.25	1.1	1.15	0.155
A/2	0.690	0.6	0.567	0.132
A/6	0.221	0.2	0.215	0.0933

TABLE V.

Composition of the residual sol.

	Sp. conductivity $\times 10^3$.	Activity of Cl' ion $\times 10^2$.	Total chlorine $\times 10^2$.	Hydrogen ion conc. $\times 10^4$.
A	1.42	1.41	0.92	1.12
A/2	1.03	0.77	0.83	1.02
A/6	0.885	0.28	0.29	0.813

TABLE VI.

Composition of the ultrafiltrate (first portion).

A	0.89210	0.741	0.650	0.468
A/2	0.578	0.407	0.363	0.398
A/6	0.189	0.166	0.135	0.347

TABLE VII.

Composition of the ultrafiltrate (second portion).

A	0.949	0.813	0.741	0.617
A/2	0.590	0.457	0.285	0.490
A/6	0.148	...

TABLE VIII.

*Cataphoretic speed of aluminium hydroxide sol with dilution
Temp. 35°.*

Upper liq.	Dilution.	Upward			Downward		
		Pot. gradient volt/cm.		Rate of migration in cms. per sec. per volt/cm. $\times 10^5$.	Pot. gradient volt/cm.		Rate of migration in cms. per sec. per volt/cm. $\times 10^5$.
		Before movement of boundary.	After movement of boundary.		Before movement of boundary.	After movement of boundary.	
Ultrafiltrate	A	0.617	0.626	34.26	0.658	0.632	34.65
	A/6	0.744	0.747	38.1	0.742	0.696	41
HCl + AlCl ₃	A	0.638	0.629	31.9	0.654	0.639	33.9
	A/2	0.724	0.708	44.5	0.691	0.68	44.2
	A/6	0.732	0.712	40	0.69	0.681	43

Changes on ultrafiltration.—In agreement with the results obtained with Fe₂O₃ sols the ultrafiltrate has a different conductivity and composition than the original sol. The conductivity of the residual sol is, however, greater but that of the ultrafiltrate is less. With the ferric oxide sol the residual sol after ultrafiltration had a smaller conductivity (Mukherjee, Roychoudhury and Biswas, *loc. cit.*). The Cl' ion concentration of the residual sol is greater with

both sols. Thus with the ferric oxide sol an increase of the Cl' ion concentration and the oxide content results in the diminution of the conductivity of the residual sol whereas with the Al₂O₃ sol an increase is observed. Evidently the distribution of the ions (Cl', Al⁺⁺⁺ and H⁺) between the intermicellary liquid and between the 'liquid' and 'solid' sides of the double layer determines the properties of the sol. The total interface and the p_H range giving the stability of the cations of the oxide also play an important rôle. It is not possible to specify the properties of such a sol unless we have definite knowledge of these factors which are responsible for the difference between the results of the two sols. Within the observed p_H range the Al⁺⁺⁺ ions are stable (p_H 3.5, 4.6) and it is not surprising that the total Cl and the Cl' ion concentration have practically the same value. The sol is rich in electrolytes and the ultrafiltrate contains aluminium and hydrogen chlorides. The constancy of the potential gradient with the ultrafiltrate as the upper liquid (*vide* Table VIII) is to be attributed to the fact that the amount of the current carried by the colloid particles is small compared with that carried by free electrolytes.*

Analysis of the aluminium oxide sols.—The results given above are summarised in the following table; u , the cataphoretic speed of the colloidal particles; U the cataphoretic speed multiplied by one Faraday; $K_{\text{obs.}}$, the observed specific conductivity; $C_{\text{Cl}'}$, the activity of Cl' ion; N_{Cl} the total chloride concentration; $C_{\text{H}^{\circ}}$, the concentration of H⁺ ion; $C_{\frac{1}{3}\text{Al}^{\text{+++}}}$ the concentration of $\frac{1}{3}\text{Al}^{\text{+++}}$ (assuming that $C_{\frac{1}{3}\text{Al}^{\text{+++}}} = C_{\text{Cl}'} - C_{\text{H}^{\circ}}$).

TABLE IX.

Dilution.	$u \times 10^{-5}$.	U .	$K_{\text{obs.}}$	$C_{\text{Cl}'}$.	N_{Cl} .	$C_{\text{H}^{\circ}}$.	$C_{\frac{1}{3}\text{Al}^{\text{+++}}}$.
A	37.3	36.5	0.00125	0.011	0.0106	0.000155	0.010845
A/2	48.0	46.34	0.00069	0.00617	0.00567	0.000132	0.006038
A/6	41.3	39.87	0.000221	0.00234	0.00215	0.000933	0.0022467

II. Experiments with Sols D, L and M.

Preparation.—A precipitate of aluminium hydroxide was obtained by adding one litre of 0.1N-ammonia solution to 1 litre of

* Mukherjee, Roychoudhury and Biswas (*loc. cit.*) have shown that the ultrafiltrate of the sol is not always satisfactory as an upper liquid for cataphoretic measurements by the moving boundary method.

0.1N-aluminium chloride. The precipitate was washed with conductivity water 9 times with the help of a powerful centrifuge. The containers were of borosilicate glass. The supernatant liquid was thrown off and the precipitate resuspended in conductivity water. In the last two washings the precipitate was suspended in 600 c.c. of water. The supernatant liquid containing colloidal aluminium oxide after the last operation of the centrifuge, was allowed to stand for 15 days and the stable sol consisting of the supernatant liquid was siphoned off (sol D). The precipitate in the container was mixed with 50 c.c. of water and 30 c.c. of the suspension were divided into portions of 10 c.c. each. All three were diluted with 500 c.c. of conductivity water. To one of these three no hydrochloric acid was added: the sol thus obtained gives sol K_0 . To the other two, 5 c.c. and 1 c.c. respectively of 0.005N-HCl were added and the sols thus obtained give sols L_0 and M_0 respectively. The object of the repeated washings was to remove traces of ammonia as far as possible. 400 C.c. of sol L_0 was diluted to 1600 c.c. with conductivity water and stocked in an atmosphere of hydrogen free from carbon dioxide, or air. This sol is sol L. Sol M was similarly obtained from sol M_0 .

The accuracy of the chlorine ion activities.—It has been seen in Part I that calomel and silver chloride electrodes give reliable and mutually agreeing values of the chlorine ion activity. The measurements of the chlorine ion activity in *dilute* hydrochloric acid solutions by the calomel electrode is rendered uncertain on account of the reaction of the dissolved oxygen (Mukherjee and Kumar, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 2179). The agreement between the calomel and silver electrodes mentioned above shows that in colloidal solutions of ferric oxide this disturbing effect is negligible. It was, however, thought desirable to prepare silver chloride electrodes in the several ways used by previous workers for the most accurate measurements and to compare the results so obtained with those with calomel electrodes. The chlorine ion activities of hydrochloric acid at two dilutions were measured with these electrodes and care was taken to render the system free from oxygen. The *E.M.F.* of the "concentration" cell is reproducible within 0.1 millivolt. The following data show the agreement between tested silver chloride electrodes and the calomel electrode:

cell : Ag/AgCl/0.0009353N-HCl/sat. KNO_3 /0.009353N-HCl/AgCl/Ag

Observed *E.M.F.* = 0.0610 volt at 35°

With Hg/HgCl electrodes *E.M.F.* observed = 0.0595 volt.

The *E.M.F.* calculated from the activity coefficients given by Randall and Young for 25° (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 989) is 0.05943 volt.

The concentrations of the free chlorine ions of sols L and M calculated from the observed activities are very low (of the order of 10^{-5}). It is well known that the measurement of chlorine ion activities by the silver—silver chloride or calomel electrodes at such low chlorine ion concentrations of simple electrolytes (*e.g.*, hydrochloric acid or potassium chloride) is uncertain. Both the silver—silver chloride and the calomel electrodes, however, gave activities which agree sufficiently well with each other. The *E.M.F.*s actually observed against 0.009353*N*-HCl are given below.

The cell combination was as follows :

TABLE X.

Aluminium hydroxide sol, sample L.

Dilution.	Ag—AgCl Electrode.		Hg—HgCl Electrode.	
	Time.	<i>E.M.F.</i> in volts.	Time.	<i>E.M.F.</i> in volts.
L	2.45 p.m.	0.1220	1.45 p.m.	0.1420
	3	0.2075	2	0.1420
	3.15	0.1425		
	3.30	0.1425		
L/2	4	0.0750	2.15	0.1285
	4.15	0.1210	2.45	0.1370
	4.30	0.1380	3.15	0.1370
	4.45	0.1360		
L/4	5	0.1075	*	0.1195 (constant value)
	5.15	0.1195		
	5.30	0.1195		
L/6	4.15	0.0625	*	0.1090
	5	0.0705		0.0720
	5.15	0.0705		0.1095
				0.1095
			0.1140 (constant value)	

* The time readings were not taken.

TABLE XI.

Aluminium hydroxide sol, sample M.

Dilution	M	M/2	M/6	M/11
Ag—AgCl electrode E.M.F. in volts.	}	...0.1809 (const. value)	0.2073	0.2080	0.2760
Hg—HgCl electrode E.M.F. in volts.					

The concentration of the total chloride was determined as before by electrometric titration which gives the best reproducibility. In some cases the chlorine ion activity of the sol treated with nitric acid and diluted to a known volume was also measured and the concentration was calculated. Care was taken to avoid loss of chlorine in dissolving the colloid in nitric acid. Volhard's method was also used. Electrometric titrations give the best results.

The arrangements for stocking the sol in an atmosphere of carefully purified hydrogen as also the difficulties arising out of the presence in the sol and leakage of carbon dioxide in titrations with alkali have been described elsewhere (Mukherjee, Roychoudhury, Das-Gupta, and Chatterjee, *Ind. Journ. Agric. Sci.*, 1932, 2, 638). The arrangements for simultaneous measurements of chlorine and hydrogen ion activities as also of the conductivity in an atmosphere free from oxygen or carbon dioxide in such titrations, of sol D have been described in the above paper. Only the results are given in this paper.

In the following tables the symbols have the significance given below :

C_{Cl} = the concentration of chlorine ions in g. ions per litre calculated from the observed activity assuming the activity coefficient to be unity.

N_{Cl} = the total chlorine concentration in g. atoms per litre.

K_{obs} = the measured specific conductivity; u = the equivalent conductivity of the charged colloidal particles obtained from the measured cataphoretic speed.

C_H = the concentration of hydrogen ions calculated as in the case of the chlorine ions.

C_{coll} or $C_{\frac{1}{3}Al^{+++}}$ = the equivalent concentration of the charged colloidal particle or the aluminium ion calculated as in the case of the ferric oxide sols (Part I); the symbol K stands for specific conductivities. The dilution is given as the ratio of the volume of the resulting sol to the volume of the initial sol.

* A very unsteady reading was obtained.

TABLE XII.

Sol.	Dilution.	$K_{\text{obs}} \times 10^5$.	$C_{\text{Cl}}' \times 10^5$.		$N_{\text{Cl}} \times 10^5$.	$C_{\text{H}^+} \times 10^5$.	u .
			Hg/Hgcl	Ag/Agcl			
D	Nil	4.94	—	2.17	2.45	0.457	25.3
L	„	0.131	4.01	3.95	40.4	0.0097	
„	2	0.0887	4.85	4.62	20.2	0.0155	
„	4	0.0764	9.57	9.39	10.1	0.0182	
„	6	0.0606	11.56	Unreliable	6.7	0.018	
M	Nil	0.0546	0.9541	0.928	9.13	0.107	
„	2	0.0506	0.3886	0.343	4.57	0.0158	
„	6	0.0415	0.3816	0.334	1.52	0.01	
„	11	0.0406	Uncertain		0.83	0.00048	

The agreement in the determination of the total chlorine in suitable cases by the different methods mentioned above is illustrated by the following data for sol I.

Volhardt's method: 3.95×10^{-4} ; electrometric titration 4.04×10^{-4} .

The aluminium contents of these sols in g. moles of aluminium oxide per litre are as follows:

sol $\equiv 0.000122$; sol L $\equiv 0.000334$; sol M $\equiv 0.00037$.

III. Experiments with Silicic Acid Sols.

The electrochemical properties of colloidal solutions of acidic and basic substances and of suspensions of such substances are being investigated in this laboratory with reference to a theoretical elucidation of the titration curves and allied reaction of colloidal acid clay. Details of these experiments are given elsewhere (Mukherjee and coworkers, *Ind. Journ. Agric. Sci.*, 1932, 2, 639 and results to be published later). For the purposes of the present paper measurements similar to those described above and carried out with a silicic acid sol (S) * and its dilutions are given below.

TABLE XIII.

Dilution.	$K_{\text{obs}} \times 10^4$.	$C_{\text{Cl}} \times 10^4$.	$N_{\text{Cl}} \times 10^4$.	$C_{\text{H}^+} \times 10^4$.	$N_{\text{Na}} \times 10^4$.	$u \times 10^5$.
S.	11.2	41.8	52	83.2	54	...
S/2	5.93	21.4	...	10.7	...	16.5
S/6	2.57	7.3	...	2.2	...	10.3

* The method of preparation of the sol is as given by Mukherjee, Roychoudhury Das-Gupta and Chatterjee (*loc. cit.*).

Calculations.

In the following calculations the equivalent conductivities at infinite dilution and at 35° have been assumed to be as follows: For sol A, its ultra filtrate and residual sol, sol D and the silicic acid sols, $H^+ = 404$; $Cl^- = 93$; $1/3 Al^{+++} = 55$; $Na^+ = 64$; for sols L and M and their dilutions the values have been used as follows: $H^+ = 397.5$; $Cl^- = 89.6$; $1/3 Al^{+++} = 53.6$. The broad conclusions arrived at are not affected by uncertainties in these values and by the limits of experimental error.

TABLE XIV.

Aluminium oxide sols.

Sol.	$K_{obs.} \times 10^4.$	$K_{calc.} \times 10^4.$			Δ_{σ}	
		Al ⁺⁺⁺		Coll. Ag/AgCl.	γ	δ
		(1) Hg/HgCl.	(2) Ag/AgCl.			
A	12.5	...	16.8	14.8	103	108.2
A/2	6.9	...	9.34	8.83	113	104.5
A/6	2.21	...	3.29	2.94	85	92.1
A ultra 1	8.92	...	11.13	117
A/2 ultra 1	5.78	...	6.16	137
A/6 ultra 1	1.89	...	2.57	103
A ultra 2	9.5	...	12.25	114
A/2 ultra 2	5.9	...	6.94	125
A 'residual'	14.2	...	21.3	90.3
A/2 'residual'	10.3	...	11.8	122.8
A/6 'residual'	3.85	...	4.43	126.5
D	0.494	...	0.048	0.043	184	156
L	0.0131	0.0574	0.0569	...	3.1	32.5
L/2	0.00887	0.0693	0.667	...	4.0	17.6
L/4	0.00744	0.137	0.134	...	6.8	7.2
L/6	0.00606	0.1661	0.0852	...	7.7	4.5
M	0.00546	0.01719	0.01696	...	0.27	3.02
M/2	0.00506	0.00586	0.00545	...	9.4	131
M/6	0.00415	0.00555	0.00512	...	24.2	113
M/11	0.00406	47.8	—

TABLE XV.

Silicic acid sol.

Dilution.	$K_{obs.} \times 10^4.$	$K_{calc.} \times 10^4.$	$K_{obs.}/K_{calc.}$
S	11.2	42.9	0.261
S/2	5.93	8.32	0.71
S/6	2.57	2.32	1.1

The silicic acid sol was prepared by dialysis from sodium silicate and hydrochloric acid and contained sodium chloride.

DISCUSSION.

The calculations given above show that there is a discrepancy between the observed and calculated conductivities. The observations with the ultrafiltrate and the residual sols also show a discrepancy. Greater care was taken in the measurements with sols D, L and M, and those with A formed the first measurements. It will be seen (a) that the observed conductivity is sometimes too high to be accounted for by the activities, *e.g.*, the ferric oxide sols; (b) that it is too small, *e.g.*, aluminium oxide sols, (c) and also the intermediate case where a good agreement is observed. The discrepancy cannot be accounted for by the possible errors in these measurements and in the calculation, as in some cases the difference is too large. The calculated values of the equivalent conductivity per free chlorine ion are widely different.

The sols having a higher p_H value, *e.g.*, M and its dilutions are likely to contain very few free aluminium ions in the intermicellary liquid and it is with these sols that one observes a very low equivalent conductivity calculated in the manner used by Pauli and Valko (*loc. cit.*).

In these calculations a correction is necessary for the conductivity of the water. The conductivity of the hydrogen ions has been taken into account, only that due to the hydroxyl ions has to be included. Its magnitude is small (excepting M_{11}) and its omission does not interfere with the broad conclusions. The dissociation of aluminium oxide as an ampholyte may also be overlooked for our present purpose; because the sum of the conductivities of the ions whose activities have been measured, *e.g.*, in the case of M, is already *several times* greater than the observed value. The increase in the hydrogen and chlorine activities observed with the dilution of sol L is remarkable. So far as the hydrogen ion activity is concerned this is not new. Such an increase has been observed with thorium oxide sol (Pauli and Valko, *loc. cit.*, p. 316) but the increase of the activity of the chlorine is remarkable.

The rapid decrease with dilution in the activity of the hydrogen ions (which are the mobile ions in the double layer) in the case of the silicic acid sol, is in contrast to the above mentioned

behaviour of the chlorine ions. This rapid increase of the hydrogen ion activity with the concentration has no parallel with known acids, strong, medium or weak. It is remarkable that the discrepancy between the observed and calculated conductivities increases rapidly with the concentration of the colloid. The cathoretic speed of the original sol could not be determined as the sol was lost. An equivalent conductivity of 20 has been assumed in the calculation.

The following results have been obtained by Mr. B. R. Majumdar with a different sample of silicic acid sol. Both hydrogen and quinhydrone electrodes were employed for measurement of the p_H values.

TABLE XVI.

Silicic acid sol (T).

Conc. = 0.4276 g. mol per litre.

Dilution.	$A_H \times 10^3$. (Fig. 1)	p_H .*
T	13.21	1.879 (H ₂ electrode) 1.96 (Quinhydrone electrode)
T/2	5.889	2.23 (H ₂ electrode) 2.33 (Quinhydrone electrode)
T/6	1.897	2.72 (H ₂ electrode) 2.41 (Quinhydrone electrode)
T/11	0.839	3.076 (H ₂ electrode) 3.077 (Quinhydrone electrode)

The variation of the H⁺ ion concentrations of the sol (Fig. 1) with its concentration confirms the previous observation (*Ind. Journ. Agric. Sci.*, 1932, 2, 638) that the sol behaves as an 'ultra-strong' acid. The increase in the activity of the hydrogen ions at a rate greater than the concentration has no parallel with any known acid in true solution. Moreover, the sol contains free electrolytes, hydrochloric acid and sodium chloride. The concentration of these

* This column shows the agreement between the values of p_H obtained by the hydrogen and quinhydrone electrodes. A_H values in the table are, however, calculated from the p_H values obtained by the hydrogen electrode.

FIG. 1.

electrolytes increases proportionately with that of the sol. Consequently in these dilute solutions on account of the increasing ionic strength, the activity coefficients should decrease more rapidly than they would with the concentration of dilute solutions of hydrochloric acid. It may be suggested that the stronger acidity is apparent and arises from an actually lower concentration of dissolved hydrogen at the immediate neighbourhood of the Pt-surface. The adhesion of a coating of flocculated particles of the sol on the surface diminishes the rate of diffusion of the hydrogen to the surface and the dissolved hydrogen at the surface is thus not in equilibrium with the gas. Against this is the fact that the sol is quite liquid, and there is no visible sign of flocculi on the electrode surface. What is more decisive is that the p_H values of the sol by both the quinhydrone and hydrogen electrodes agree. Rabinowitsch and Laskin (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, 134, 387) have also found that both electrodes give results in mutual agreement. These facts go against

another possible explanation, namely, that there is a greater concentration of the primary particles of the sol on the electrode surface resulting from gelation but no diminished H_2 pressure. In case, gelation or diminished hydrogen pressure was responsible for the observed curvature, both quinhydrone and hydrogen electrodes could not have given identical p_H values. The results therefore leave no doubt as to the real nature of the manner of increase in the activity with the concentration and of the manner of the variation of the activity coefficient. Further investigations are necessary to find out how far this is due to a progressive replacement of the primarily adsorbed hydrogen ions by the increasing concentrations of sodium ions (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 191; *Kolloid Z.*, 1929, 49, 362).

The 'chemical' theory does not contemplate discrepancies of the type revealed in the above calculations. The analogy with electrolytic systems fails in the case of the sols with higher p_H . Neither can the Helmholtz-Smoluchowski theory account for the higher value of the observed conductivity, *e.g.*, in the case of ferric oxide sols, nor can it account quantitatively for the very low values of the equivalent conductivity. It is possible to imagine that the activity measurements indicate concentrations different from those used in the calculations. The agreement between the total chlorine concentration and that calculated from the activity renders this explanation doubtful in cases where such an agreement has been observed. The other possibility is that the calculation of the hydrogen ion concentration from activity is at fault. But this cannot explain the extremely low equivalent conductivity observed with sol M. Here the equivalent conductivity obtained by dividing the observed sp. conductivity (multiplied by 1000) by the chlorine ion concentration is about 59. The equivalent conductivity calculated similarly for M_2 , and M_6 are respectively 147 and 124. This difference cannot be referred to a special error in the measurements with sol M. Sols L_1 , L_2 , L_4 , and L_6 have the values 32.6, 18.3, 7.98 and 5.2. These extremely low values are irreconcilable with the Helmholtz-Smoluchowski theory provided the calculated chlorine ion concentration really indicates the actual value.

The cataphoretic speeds change in an irregular manner with the dilution. This is in contrast with the uniform decrease in the specific conductivity observed on dilution in all cases. It is not possible to account for the variations in the cataphoretic speed as arising out of changes in the ionic strength as Pauli and Valko

(*loc. cit.*) have assumed to be the case. The simultaneous measurement of the cataphoretic speed renders invalid the main assumption of Pauli and Valko (*loc. cit.*) that the equivalent conductivity of the colloid ion can account for the observed conductivity. The colloidal ion behaves in a specific manner with respect to its conductivity; also the associated free ions (the mobile ions) show a characteristic behaviour with reference to their activities and conductivities.

The Figure 2 shows the changes in the chlorine and hydrogen ion activities and of the conductivity (all measured simultaneously in an atmosphere of very pure hydrogen) of sol D on titration with a baryta solution. It will be seen that (a) the free positive charges reacting with the hydroxyl ions is less than that calculated from the total chlorine or the chlorine ion activity, and (b) there is a diminution in the chlorine ion activity on the

FIG. 2.

addition of the first amounts of the baryta. These observations go against the assumption of an activity coefficient of about unity for the chlorine ions, which is apparently indicated by the agreement between the total chlorine and the chlorine ion concentration calculated from the activity measurements.

It is necessary to state here that the concentrations of hydrogen and chlorine ions have been calculated from their activities which are fairly reproducible and the observed *E.M.F.s.* were satisfactorily steady. The liquid junction potential though small is unknown and there is a magnification of the error in calculating the concentration of the ions from their activities which are logarithmic functions of the concentrations. It thus becomes necessary only to emphasise those cases where the difference between the calculated and observed conductivities cannot be accounted for by these uncertainties. The magnification of error in calculating the concentration of the ions from their activities obviously depends on the value of the mantissa of the logarithm. It ranges in most cases from 6 to 18% assuming an error of 2 millivolts in the *E. M. F.* The data given above show that the discrepancy is, at least in some cases, too great to be accounted for by these uncertainties. Sol D (*vide* Table XIV) forms a very exceptional example. The specific conductivity of 9.5×10^5 is more than ten times greater than the calculated one. One finds similar extremes also in Muttone and Pauli's data (*Kolloid Z.*, 1931, 57, 212). The figures given in the following table (XVII) have been calculated from the values given by Muttone and Pauli (*loc. cit.*) in Table V of their paper. It will be seen that for sol 5, the observed specific conductivity is ten times the calculated one.

The behaviour of these colloidal solutions presents features not met with usual electrolytes and further investigation is necessary to elucidate the characteristics of some systems.

TABLE XVII.

Sol.	Conc. of Al_2O_3 in g. mole per litre.	A_{H_2O}	A_{Cl}	$A_{1/3Al} \dots$ or $A_{colloid} = A_{Cl} - A_H$	$A_H \times 394 = X$	$A_{Cr} \times 75.4 = Y$	$A_{1/3Al} \dots \times 456 = Z$	$u \times 10^5$ cm./sec. per volt/cm.	$U = (u \times 96540)$	$Z = A_{colloid} \times U$	Observed sp. conductivity $\times 10^3$.	Calc. sp. conductivity $\times 10^3$.	
												$X + Y + Z$.	$X + Y + Z'$
1	0.2451	2.01×10^{-5}	5.8×10^{-2}	5.798×10^{-2}	7.015×10^{-3}	4.373	2.644	39.02	37.67	2.184	11.5	7.024	6.5642
2	0.2254	1.40×10^{-5}	4.5×10^{-2}	4.499×10^{-2}	4.884×10^{-3}	3.393	2.051	25.58	24.69	1.111	9.8	5.449	4.5089
3	0.2480	6.81×10^{-6}	3.25×10^{-2}	3.249×10^{-2}	2.376×10^{-3}	2.451	1.481	21.87	21.1	0.6855	9.1	3.934	3.1389
4	0.2941	4.90×10^{-6}	2.5×10^{-2}	2.499×10^{-2}	1.71×10^{-3}	1.885	1.14	14.85	14.34	0.3583	8.2	3.0267	2.2450
5	0.2594	4.70×10^{-6}	6.67×10^{-3}	6.665×10^{-3}	1.64×10^{-3}	0.5029	0.304	16.04	15.84	0.1031	6.05	0.8085	0.6076

SUMMARY.

1. In continuation of the first paper of this series it has been shown, that contrary to the assumptions of the supporters of the chemical school, the conductivity and activity measurements of colloidal solutions of ferric and aluminium oxide sols show characteristic differences from the known behaviour of electrolytes. The measured specific conductivity is in some cases (a) too great, and (b) in other cases too small to be reconciled with the activity measurements. The intermediate case of a satisfactory agreement is also observed.

2. The experimental evidence in support of the above statement is as follows:

(a) The specific conductivities of the ferric oxide sols, the activities of the ions which have been given in Part I, have been calculated from the latter. The values so obtained are very much lower than the observed specific conductivities. This statement is in agreement with the observations of Pauli and coworkers that the observed specific conductivity of *some* ferric oxide sols required an equivalent conductivity of 118 units at 25° for the positively charged carriers of electricity present in the sol. No such cation is so far known in electrochemistry. Unfortunately the hydrogen ion activity of these solutions cannot be directly measured and Pauli and coworkers measured it after coagulations with potassium chloride. In the experiments in Part I the coagulation was carried out with potassium sulphate. It has been observed from this laboratory that the p_H of the supernatant liquid depends on the coagulating electrolyte and to a lesser extent on its amount. The p_H increases comparatively slightly on the addition of larger amounts of the solid electrolyte. It is thus likely that the sol has a different and perhaps a higher hydrogen ion concentration than that estimated by the above mentioned indirect method. It is, however, doubtful whether the actual p_H of the sol is so low as to account for the observed conductivity.

(b) Aluminium oxide sols have the advantage that the hydrogen ion activity can be directly measured. Pauli and Valko (*loc. cit.*) have shown that this sol shows a constant proportionality between the equivalent activity and the equivalent conductivity of the colloid chloride. They arrive at an equivalent conductivity of about 145

units for the colloid chloride at 25° which signifies that the cataphoretic speed of the colloidal particles should be about 70 units at 25° . On calculation from their data one finds that the observed conductivity is systematically *lower* than that calculated from the activities assuming that the activity coefficient is equal to unity. It is also found that the equivalent conductivity at infinite dilution calculated according to the assumptions made by them decreases with the higher dilutions. This sol used by them had p_{H} values ranging from 2 to 4. As free aluminium ions are likely to be present in considerable quantities in such solutions, evidence for their presence has been sought to be obtained from the analysis of the ultrafiltrate. Experiments have been described with sols having higher p_{H} and these show that there is a real discrepancy between the activity and the conductivity measurements. The equivalent conductivity of the colloid chloride is sometimes very low, in fact so low that the Helmholtz-Smoluchowski theory which contemplates that the current carried by the charged colloidal particle and its associated mobile ions is wholly measured by the cataphoretic speed multiplied by the free charge of the particle, cannot also account for these low values. The significance of the activity measurement has been briefly discussed.

(c) Observations with silicic acid sols (S) corroborate the above conclusions.

(d) Results of further experiments with a silicic acid sol (T) containing sodium chloride confirm that the activity of the hydrogen ion increases more rapidly than the concentration of the sol, although the total concentrations of electrolytes in the sol correspond to the region of dilute solutions.

(e) Calculations of the specific conductivities of aluminium hydroxide sols from the data obtained by Muttone and Pauli *loc. cit.*) also show considerable discrepancy between the observed and calculated specific conductivities.

(f) Colloidal solutions thus show a behaviour characteristic of themselves and further investigations are desirable.